

Application of neural networks to digital pulse shape analysis for an array of silicon strip detectors

Authors:

J. L. Flores ^a, I. Martel ^{b,d}, R. Jiménez ^c, J. Galán ^c, P. Salmerón ^a

^a Dpto de Ingeniería Eléctrica y Térmica, Universidad de Huelva, Spain

^b Dpto de Física Aplicada, Universidad de Huelva, Spain

^c Dpto de Ingeniería Electrónica, Sist. Informáticos y Automática, Universidad de Huelva, Spain

^d CERN, ISOLDE, CH 1211 Geneva, 23, Switzerland

Abstract:

The new generation of nuclear physics detectors that used to study nuclear reactions is considering the use of digital pulse shape analysis techniques (DPSA) to obtain the (A,Z) values of the reaction products impinging in solid state detectors. This technique can be an important tool for selecting the relevant reaction channels at the HYDE (HYbrid DETector ball array) silicon array foreseen for the Low Energy Branch of the FAIR facility (Darmstadt, Germany). In this work we study the feasibility of using artificial neural networks (ANNs) for particle identification with silicon detectors. Multilayer Perceptron networks were trained and tested with recent experimental data, showing excellent identification capabilities with signals of several isotopes ranging from ¹²C up to ⁸⁴Kr, yielding higher discrimination rates than any other previously reported.

Keywords:

HYDE, FAIR, Neural networks, Digital pulse shape analysis, Silicon detectors

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